

Six Ideological Limits in the Representation of the Rural People

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Abstract

Embarking on a journey to undertake a reflection exercise on contemporary rural human implies a double deconstruction. The first proceeds under the assumption that the existence of rural humans is identifiable and analysable in the field of thinking and representation. Ranging from symbolic valorization to the simple deictic gesture, the existence of the rural human cannot be understood unless it undergoes a deconstruction exercise. On the other side, a second deconstruction is generated by a positioning issue in the critical field: to what extent are we still contemporary with the idea of a rural human in the peasant sense of country life? Furthermore, what are the updated conditions of rurality in terms of roles and profiles that may establish a so-called common place of the rural human? Once these two deconstructions have been carried out, the other two interrogative lines emerge as a result of our interpretative effort to reconfigure a possible discourse on the contemporary rural human. First, it is necessary to understand if reconfiguring the contemporary rural human makes the subject of an update a matter of rural anthropology. And, particularly here, we need to tread lightly since such a project oscillates between a salvage project (especially of the rural tradition) and a reinvestment activity (modernizing the rural life in the context of globalization). Secondly, we should avoid placing this type of reconstruction within the urban centrist discourse on the urban-rural relationship. The rural-urban symbolic and spatial continuum is not defined by the antinomic accents of the urban-rural relationship, and, under no circumstances, involves a hierarchy. We need a different approach and understanding of rurality, rural fact, and rural human in this urban-rural continuum. What are our speculative resources necessary for such an endeavour? First, we need to identify the mental frameworks we use to represent the rural human, the limits ideologically drawn for understanding and perceiving it. Six of these limits, the most relevant ones, are being discussed in this paper. Their relevance stems from their symbolic and ideological effects, as well as their power to structure the representations and discourses about the contemporary rural human. It concerns the rural-urban relationship, the rural categories (peri-urban, medium, and deep rural), the difference between community and association, the rural human's bond with the agricultural activities, new ruralism, and the relationship between peasants and rural humans.

Keywords: Rural, Limits, Contemporary rural people, Rural-urban continuum

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Argument. Rural-urban continuum and the representation of the contemporary rural human

If I were to undertake a deconstructive exercise, in which we would remove the symbolic weight of population density, we could notice that cities are actually rare and atypical in a world that appears completely rural. We would then represent reality as a world of wide-open spaces, where cities are mere islands of a weird way of living. Still, such a reductive exercise does not long withstand our way of thinking and representing the relationship between urban and rural, since we live in a society that makes its speeches starting from an ideology particularly focused on urban values. The speculative exercise employed here has been used merely to underscore our strong adherence to a primarily urban way of understanding, describing, and exploiting reality.

On the other hand, as a result of globalization, the urbanization of lifestyle has definitely and irremediably imposed itself as a successful model in rural environments. The progress of transport and communications infrastructure, the expansion of services and the business environment, and the growth of entrepreneurial culture are just a few of the global phenomena that have accelerated the replication of urban lifestyle in rural areas.

However, regardless of how profound its effects are, globalization has lately given rise to counter-reactionary phenomena. Local and glocal reactions (as an attempt to balance between supporting local values in the context of globalization) lead to a rediscovery of the countryside, a reinvention, and even a re-idealization of it. These reactions may embrace an identitarian character, with nostalgic and restorative tones, but they can also be influenced by an entrepreneurial pragmatism, especially in the rural tourism sector.

In this context, we can discuss the revaluation of rurality and, under the pressure of urban culture, the erosion of peasant traditions. We are thus facing an antinomy. The urban human, growingly tired of the city's hustle and bustle, not to mention pollution, wishes for a countryside less affected by globalization, as a possible symbolic anchor for an idyllic holiday or later retirement. By contrast, the rural human, affected by a certain isolation, wishes for a modern, more efficient way of living, as he believes the urban human does.

By all appearances, these phenomena are a direct consequence of development. The global modernization of resource use and the universal shift in values regarding lifestyle and quality of life appear to be the main factors contributing to this antinomy. However, I believe that such an explanation is insufficient, since modernization and emancipation are inevitable. I rather think that the lack of a lasting and sustainable approach to development is what produces these phenomena of pressure and contamination. Under the circumstances, the representation of the rural human is often made by appealing to urban concepts, narratives, and representations.

Apart from strictly anthropological interests, which require understanding rural populations in situ, the profile of the rural person is constituted mainly through an amalgamation of rural and urban discourses. And this amalgamation claims to be a novel tool for interpretation. Thus, the rural-urban continuum can be used here as a theoretical model, based on which we can analyse the representations of contemporary rural humanity in the discourse universe of symbolic relations, both symbolic and material, between the rural and the urban.

At the level of representations, the rural-urban continuum alludes to a discourse universe in which we can only represent reality as either urban or rural, or at the threshold between the two. From a conceptual standpoint, the expression has a double epistemological effect: it refers both to the material relationship between urban and rural regions, and to the conditions of possibility of urban or rural environments..

Beyond conceptualizing the urban and rural worlds, this conceptual model provides us with the epistemological tools for defining the contemporary rural human as well. In other words, conceptualizing the rural-urban continuum as a discourse universe opens the possibility of speaking about the rural human through triangulations. Therefore, when referring to the contemporary rural human, we will always be subject to discourses revolving around their ruralism, their urban projection, or around the mixture of urban and rural representations. Consequently, the definition limits of the rural man can also be influenced by the urban-rural continuum and, through this, by rural, urban, or both urban and rural perspectives. The profile of the contemporary rural human is, for now, at the centre of interactions between various discourses and representations that no longer show clearly a rural or urban affiliation.

Under the circumstances, conceptually speaking, the rural and urban can be regarded as social realities, with the stress on the fact that rural implies a double course of symbolical constitution in terms of representation. This is not constituted exclusively at the level of identity narratives in rural spaces, but rather at the intersection of the symbolic projections of rural humans with those of urban humans. In other words, the rural human appears to us under a socio-economic profile of rural reality, constituted not at the level of their own representations, but at the level of all the representations that call them into question.

Concerning the limits under which the profile of the contemporary rural human is defined, methodologically speaking, I must specify that I will understand them in the double sense of the concept of limit, the double meaning perceived by Immanuel Kant in the Critique of Pure Reason (Kant 2009). Thus, in a first understanding, limits represent delimitations, constraints, conditionings, and obstacles that cannot be overcome. In this sense, limits have a negative character simply because they limit us. But precisely because they have this meaning of conditioning, limits also become the only tools we have to know reality. They open up the space of possibility for the knowing subject. And, in our interpretative project, this double

meaning of limits endows them with an epistemological character. Accordingly, on one hand, through their negative character, limits provide us with the conditions of possibility for the conceptualization and representation of rural humans. On the other hand, because of their positive nature, limits also serve to structure the discourses through which we try to understand contemporary rural humans. Further, it should be specified that, depending on the interests of interpretation, numerous such limits can be identified. However, the six limits I have chosen to expose here are the most important and the most frequent in public discourses. Therefore, it concerns the limits imposed by the rural-urban relationship, categories of the rural (periurban, medium rural, and deep rural), the distinction between community and association, the bond of rural folk with agricultural activities, neoruralism, and the relationship between peasants and rural humans.

The rural-urban relationship as a limit in understanding the rural human

The first limit in our discourses and representations about the rural human is imposed by the rural-urban dichotomy. The rural and urban have always been pitted against each other, either for simple descriptive reasons or for strategic or ideological ones. And this opposition has produced, at the level of representations, an exclusive and exhaustive disjunction of these two social realities. Thus, everything related to social systems is either rural or urban. In this classical opposition, the metropolitan is characterized by high population density and serves as a hub for industrial work, commerce, services, and governance. The rural, on the other hand, is responsible for agricultural work and has a direct relationship with nature. From this perspective, when referring to the rural world, we often picture an idyllic agrarian world. And, in this system of representation, the rural rather expresses the exteriority of the urban, in the different degrees and various nuances that such a projection produces.

Conversely, in public speeches, it is often noted that urban human is increasingly exposed to an existential crisis. Current events expose us to an urban existentialism in all the classic terms of existentialism. Therefore, the urban human feels increasingly disconnected from nature, from an idyllic life that rural surroundings could offer. Although they are not yet willing to give up the socio-economic comfort that the city offers them, the urban individual lives in permanent frustration with the rural world. They feel that they are in a permanent state of disconnection from the rural idyll. The simple act of going out to a barbecue during the summer season prompts us to think that city dwellers yearn for a resumption of ties with a romantic countryside they feel they have lost.

As a counterpoint, there are also rural frustrations and existential concerns: rural individuals experience a certain frustration with the standards of living the urban world offers; they lack

the opportunities and tools that city dwellers have. And to have these urban opportunities and devices, which they know will improve their lives, they are willing to give up their rural lifestyle and adopt strategies and models common to big cities.

In this regard, whether it is about rural or urban individuals, when we are dealing with the representation of our own identity, the discourses become somewhat mixed. Which, from a logical point of view, requires an exclusive relationship, and from an ideological point of view acquires an Alexandrian character, in the sense that the representations diversify and interpenetrate. Accordingly, if rural and urban can be operationalized to represent socio-economic realities, they become critical when referring to the way of life and everything we want, whether we are rural or urban people. Because when it comes to quality of life, things become more complicated, and the rural-urban opposition is no longer sufficient.

Conversely, when this opposition is placed at a symbolic level, the rural area loses, as most representations portray it as inferior to the urban area. Underdevelopment, rudimentary lifestyle, subculture, and dialectal speech are common characteristics that public discourse attributes to the rural environment. Outside the episodic nostalgic moments when rural life is idealized for its connection to nature and tradition, the rural is generally regarded as the common ground of the barbarian, a concept embedded in our rhetoric since Ancient Greece. It is the mysterious realm where the absolute stranger resides, partly because they are mysterious and cannot be fully understood: their lifestyle is different, and their language is also unintelligible. This is how it worked until not so long ago, which is still evident in our discourses and representations, commonly amplified by the fact that in the 20th century, a profound conflict arose between rural and urban individuals stemming from the migration of the so-called peasants to the city.

Nevertheless, even at a symbolic level, things have changed fundamentally. The pluses and minuses, as well as the superiorities and inferiorities, have been redistributed and increasingly depend on contextual criteria, such as pollution, access to services, demographic density, isolation, infrastructure, digital transformation, and others. We are beginning to stop thinking of rural areas as inferior and urban areas as superior, and we are trying to understand, more and more, that we are facing two environments with specific opportunities and problems. We are no longer dealing with stark oppositions at a systemic level. The exhaustive and exclusive opposition between the city as a whole and the village in general is no longer relevant for the understanding of both the urban and the rural.

At the level of general representations, the relationship between the urban and the rural becomes more relaxed. It carries additional nuances and provokes critical rather than immediate reporting.

This is why we consider the rural-urban binomial becomes even subtler when relating to the following categories, which will be analyzed later: urban, periurban, accessible rural, medium rural, and deep rural. In other words, when we discuss the second limit of our understanding of the rural individual.

Urban, periurban, accessible rural, deep rural

The second limit stems from the categories of the urban-rural continuum, specifically in terms of geographical and socioeconomic localization: urban, periurban, medium rural, and deep rural. In this context, urban is the central point, while all the other delimitations generate various degrees of distance from the centre, which is the city, both in terms of commercial connections and the regional distribution of work tasks.

Accordingly, in the first relationship of this type, if the urban represents the reference point, the periurban is symbolically characterized by proximity and exclusion, as it is perceived as a sort of antechamber to the city centre. The population here is made up of those moving to the outskirts of the city and those who manage to reach the periphery of the town. This removal involves three possible scenarios: either the city expands upon them, or they are pushed from the center to the outskirts, or they migrate from the countryside and establish a bridgehead as close as possible to urban life.

Moving on to the next delimitation, I would say that the accessible rural is the rural environment by excellence, self-sustainable both in economic terms (in socioeconomic partnership with urban centers) and in terms of identity (developing outside urban life, within its own identitarian discourses).

What is interesting, on the other hand, is that in all these delimitations, the deep rural, at the level of representations, appears as a third party of the rural-urban relationship. The deep rural, both in material and ideological terms, seems cut off from everything urban and even from what it means to be rural. Unable to be self-sustainable and living on the edge of survival, at the mercy of the natural environment, humans from deep rural areas find themselves in a profound symbolic rupture in their relationship with both medium rural and urban. They exist or are excluded from the rural pact that the middle rural makes with the metropolitan.

Based on these delimitations, I present an extended model of the urban-rural relationship here. A model in which urban centralism and rural dependence on the world of cities become especially visible. The model is concentric, and the differences are expressed in terms of distance, infrastructure, and access to services (for rural people) or resources (for urban people). Even if it is a geographically represented model, its structure is dynamic, mainly determined by access and functionalities.

These concentric figures represent a bidirectional representation of rurality. On the one hand (as a reaction), it is a delimitation of the rural according to an urban axis mundi, with added authority and functionalities, with decision-making power, with aspirational values and instruments. On the other hand (as a counter-reaction), it concerns a delimitation of the urban depending on the marginal character that the rural space acquires (limit, distance, exclusion, but also transcendence of the idyllic). This borderline character is typically perceived negatively in terms of services, infrastructure, and decision-making authority. Still, it is perceived positively in terms of tradition, healthy food, religious life, and connection with nature.

Accordingly, a discourse with theoretical objectives, based on which we classify housing as urban, peri-urban, or rural, can become an ideological tool, limiting representation, understanding, and expression in discourses about rural people. Operationally speaking, these distinctions have a clear descriptive nature and produce important explanatory resources. However, we must always be aware of the ideological risk they entail.

The rural and the urban between community and association

The third limit in understanding rural man is R. E. Pahl's famous distinction between community and association (Pahl 1968). Although R. E. Pahl has always drawn attention to the risks of interpreting his idea in this sense, his philosophy nevertheless leads to certain interpretations that view community as specific mainly to the rural, and association specific mainly to the urban. Therefore, the concept of community refers to strong interpersonal bonds within groups that tend towards a shared moral and cultural identity. Within these groups, strong cohesions tend to develop between members. This is especially noticeable in rural areas.

By contrast, the concept of association seems particularly specific to urban areas and refers to social systems characterized by a low degree of interpersonalization of the social relationships, but with a high degree of rationalization of social relations, aimed at increasing the socioeconomic efficiency of housing and lifestyle.

The community, particularly in a rural environment, can be a successful model for interpersonal communication, while the association can be a successful model for the rational organization of social life. Thus, the community, although primarily targeted at rural individuals, can become attractive to urban individuals, who, in the contemporary world, feel increasingly alienated. Conversely, the association, which is particularly relevant to urban individuals, can become appealing to the rural individual as a model of socioeconomic success.

At the same time, the differences between community and association are related to representation models of social cohesion and are supported by discourses that express at least two main ideas.

First, we represent the rural community almost as an extension of the family. It is particularly defined as a clan or community of clans. In this case, the boundaries between public and private evolve into a *modus vivendi* of the community.

Alternatively, we represent our urban community as a neural network of families who live together, interact at the level of the entire urban system, but limit their interpersonal communication only to the level of individuals or families with whom they already have a personal tradition of communication.

From this perspective, rural social interactions may appear stronger. However, things are not exactly like that, since rural people are always subject to a model of social interaction centered on the idea of convenience. They are always asked to respond and adapt to a set of common values and practices. There is a centralism here too, and it is one of the values and the acceptance of these values. The seamless dissolution of the limits between private and public space may actually represent a social horizon of alienation and stress enforced by the individual's continuous conformity to the community. Thus, the difference in conviviality between the idea of community and association can lead us to the notion that the rural human is universal in their village, but can hide certain aspects regarding their socialization pressures, with effects that can lead to alienation.

The connection between rural people and agricultural activities

One of the most significant limitations in our representation of rural people is the fact that we perceive the countryside as an area where agricultural activities prevail. It is not entirely false, but, in this symbolic system, the countryside becomes the space that provides urban people with most of the resources for food consumption. In such a context, the countryside is understood as a world par excellence of agrarian activity: it is defined by agricultural fields, pastures, meadows, orchards, hayfields, industrial farms, microfarms, apiaries, greenhouses, solariums, and vegetable gardens. Conversely, this also marks the ideological horizon in which the figure of the peasant overlaps with the profile of the land worker. Thus, the figure of the rural man is almost synonymous with the figure of the peasant, in his capacity as a land worker. If we are to discuss the rural human, based on our representations, we feel obliged to open the file on the peasant. The differences between the peasant and the rural individual become noticeable only when we have the clear intention of specifying and using them.

The discursive effects are significant, particularly in terms of representing the rural fact. We think of the rural mainly as a peasant, agricultural, distant, almost foreign realm and, at the same time, administratively subordinate to the urban world. Thus, we conceptualize the rural, especially in the form of a rationalization of living, as dependent on the work and exchange relations within the rural environment and in its relationship with the urban environment (whether it concerns symbolic or material productions and exchanges). And although the urban world has historically appeared at the intersection of rural worlds, through agglomeration phenomena, through this association between the rural individual, the peasant, and agricultural labor, we think of the rural world mainly as an effect of the dilution of urban values. We thus imagine a rural area always in exile: as if the rural human is the one who has been expelled from the city, their sole role being to ensure work on the land.

Nevertheless, the rural world is not merely a peasant world. Furthermore, the peasant as such can no longer be represented as they were in the common mentality of past centuries, when we spoke of their dependence on the land in its various forms. Naturally, agricultural economic activities are fundamental in understanding the rural world, but they are no longer sufficient in correctly understanding the rural human. Neo-ruralism, which we will discuss further, also contributes to this updating of the understanding of the current rural individual.

Neo-ruralism as a limit to the understanding and representation of rural people

The relationship between rural and urban, as we have understood it so far, has fundamentally changed and lies under the sign of glocalism (the term glocalism is a neologism produced from the fusion of globalism and localism). By integrating global and local, we believe the classical paradigm of ruralism is no longer sufficient to understand the rural individual. Because, despite globalization, we are dealing with an erosion of the authority of the urban or centralist discourse in what concerns rural description or qualification. Present-day realities, as understood in the strong concepts of globalization (postindustrialization, posthumanism, neo-ruralism), are not only vastly different but also much more complex. Downright mixed. The countryside, as we have previously imagined it, no longer abides by our traditional representations. The classical paradigm of ruralism is no longer adequate for relating to the contemporary rural human. We could thus speak of a neo-ruralist paradigm.

In its original historical context, neo-ruralism expresses a reaction to the contemporary existentialism of the urban individual, characterized by a certain pessimism and an intense dissatisfaction with city life. Relocating to the countryside and reintegration with nature is an increasingly popular option for urban dwellers who are displeased with their daily lives. But the very fact of moving to the country, living in the countryside, or increasingly exploring the

rural world, puts new pressure (this time symbolic) on the representation of the rural human. This new pressure produces at least two effects. On the one hand, the rural individual begins to be reconfigured in terms of a peasant identity, which often embodies notes of authenticity, naturalism, the idea of a healthy life, or a peaceful life. Keeping things in proportion, it seems that we are witnessing a new El Dorado, which comes with the promise of a new human reborn in a new world. A new human being, this time, who returns to nature and has an immediate connection with nature. We are thus witnesses to the birth of a new romanticism, post-industrial this time. On the other hand, a phenomenon of emancipation also occurs, through which the rural individuals distance themselves from the peasant consciousness that we typically attribute to them in our urban understanding. And this distancing becomes significant, imposing new existential demands.

Thus, the non-rural humans seem to reconfigure themselves, from now on, between the desire to be peasants or not. This is a good opening for interpreting the next limit: the one established by the relationship between the peasant and the rural human. From a sociological perspective, the conceptual distance between the peasant and the rural individual is minimal, which is related to proximate gender and specific differences.

Accordingly, the peasant is the rural human, yet not all rural individuals are peasants, due to either their roles or status resulting from their daily activities. From this standpoint, rural human is the technical supercategory of the peasant, designating any inhabitant of the administrative-territorial units defined as communes, in opposition to the city. Therefore, the peasant can be recognized by at least 2 marks, namely general and specific marks. We have a series of general marks: the peasant works in agriculture, is a so-called local individual (a son or daughter of the village), is part of the extended rural family (family relationships are powerful, with often cases of cohabitation spanning several generations), and so on. It is worth noting that, in the field of literature, general brands contribute significantly to the symbolic or ideological charge of the literary text, because they refer to roles with a highly symbolic character and to strong relationships in rural communities. Additionally, we have a series of specific marks: they worked in collective farming (being, obviously, a pensioner), is a day laborer in village work, is an individual agricultural producer, taxed or not, sells their products mainly in the city (contributing to the rural-urban dichotomy or continuum), respects social rituals and, especially, religious ones, has a rather pragmatic relationship with animals, feels attached to property or is the person who proudly calls themselves a "peasant".

Unlike general marks, which I said mainly give the ideology of a literary text, specific marks contribute to the narrative substance of discourses and ideologies. They are very dynamic, have a realistic character, and also have the advantage of presenting interesting aspects of the conflict between rural and urban consciousness. Yet, beyond these roles, the following questions are critical: "Can we still talk about the peasant today?" "Does this social category

still exist, becoming increasingly a simple symbolic category?" "Can we still open the file of the peasant and the peasantry, or should we rather turn our attention to the rural man?" At least in our field, this issue is becoming more and more important. And we believe that this is also determined by the fact that, for the term peasant, we have at least four meanings:

- An ethnological, critical, and descriptive, or scientific acceptance, based on which the peasant becomes an anthropological category (the human of sociological research, defined by cultural, historical, anthropological, aesthetic, ethical, semiological, or semiotic codes);
- A symbolic consent, through which we appeal to the idea of authenticity of the rural human, and, most often, to the repository of discursive capitalization of this meaning is literature;
- A pejorative meaning, referring especially to migrants from rural to urban areas - in this sense, the playwright Valentin Nicolau provides us with an exciting term, namely "city-peasants" (Nicolau 2000);
- Last but not least, a socio-economic acceptance by which we designate either a social category of rural residents, or a category from the labor field, with reference to the person who works in agriculture.

Instead of conclusions

Bringing all these limits up into debate, one of the chief questions about rurality is whether we can think of the rural outside the rural-urban relationship. Can we step out of this dialectics that has defined the main significances of the rural? Can we come to an understanding of rurality in relation to its own phenomena, out of certain contaminated representations coming from the rural-urban dialectics? The question is not easy. Because, first of all, we should ask ourselves which determining phenomena compel us to place the understanding of the rural in the rural-urban dialectics. Concerning these phenomena, we are primarily dealing with a purely logical aspect. The two notions that exhaust the discursive universe of the inhabited world are the urban and the rural. In other words, we are dealing with an exclusive and exhaustive situation: urban and rural are opposite notions, and the inhabited world can be either rural or urban but not both (with the specific gradients already mentioned).

This state of affairs, which concerns our language and thinking, has a critical impact on the operational level of conceptualizing the rural, as it leads us to the idea that the rural and the urban should be understood concurrently and in opposition. It concerns a logical relation provided by language that is hardly treated as suspicious. Yet, this opposition, when governed by symbolism, has the rural to lose. As already mentioned, most representations place the rural in an inferior position to the urban. How could we, therefore, carry on reducing the mental energy of the rural-urban dichotomy? Methodologically, the approach should be phenomenological. Accordingly, a phenomenological reduction of both rural and urban should identify the fundamental data of these two worlds in exclusive relation to the given specificity

of each one. To understand the rural and urban in their specific phenomena, and not in the dichotomy opened by representations. Rural is understood as rural, and urban is seen as urban. Nevertheless, this approach poses the risk of getting a new type of dialectics, perhaps a stronger one. And to avoid this risk, after the phenomenological reduction, we should undertake a critical projection of a new kind of common place for rural and urban. We should speak on the threshold of this theoretical construct of the rural-urban continuum, in which we identify not centers and peripheries, but roles, actions, discourses, and relationships.

Let us try to understand that there is rurality and a rural way of life because a certain community has ideologically constructed a rural design of reality. Things turn circular, and this is precisely where rurality must be put into question through a critique of the rural fact. In other words, to remove the understanding of rurality from the antinomic urban-rural relationship, and to introduce it into its own phenomenology, we must intervene in the analysis of rurality through a critical interpretation of the rural fact. A possible hermeneutic circle opens here. The rural fact becomes the key critical instrument for interpreting the rurality of the rural human in his own phenomenology.

Accordingly, the rural human, understood in the discursive horizon of the rural fact, becomes the very key to representing the contemporary rural man. A critical key, freed from old dichotomies and much more attentive to current phenomena, to new ideologies and to the effects of a new type of civilization that is increasingly happening in this rural-urban continuum. Naturally, this is a new positioning with an ideological character and symbolic interventions, but it is a line of reconceptualization that is worth trying.

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Author presentation - Codrin Dinu Vasiliu

- I am open and interested in participating as a researcher or facilitator in any type of projects funded by the European Commission. My primary academic training is based on philosophy, with a particular interest in the theory of interpretation, gnoseology, knowledge ecosystems, systems thinking, and digital anthropology. In my research projects, I position myself in the exploratory, speculative domain, ranging from theoretical and methodological modeling to applied knowledge practices that can serve as educational or decision-making models. In this aspect, I am concerned with the practical philosophy and possible applications of speculative discourse in contemporary anthropology (visual, digital, rural anthropology, and knowledge transfer). I have a systemic, consolidated, and complex experience in knowledge and action management for the theoretical and practical frameworks related to urban systems, rural development, knowledge transfer, living and policy labs, stakeholder communities, open science, participatory knowledge, governance, and growth. I developed and contributed to concepts, models, methodologies, toolkits, and strategies for local, regional, national, and European projects.

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